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Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) Chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) benzoic acid and 3-(*N*-2-furfuralideneimino) propionic acid.

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A perusal of the literature^{1,2} reveals that no systematic studies have been carried out on the bivalent metal chelates of *o*-(*N*- α -furfuralideneimino) benzoic acid (HFB) and 3-(*N*-2-furfuralideneimino) propionic acid (HFP) and hence the same was undertaken. HFB and HFP metal chelates were synthesised according to the literature procedure³.

Elemental analysis, molecular weight, magnetic moment, absorption and conductance data of the chelates are given in Table-1.

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS, CONDUCTANCE, ABSORPTION DATA AND MOLAR EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF SOME BIVALENT CHELATES OF *o*-(*N*- α -FURFURALIDENEIMINO) BENZOIC ACID AND 3-(*N*-2-FURFURALIDENEIMINO) PROPIONIC ACID.

Composition	Molecular weight		μ_{eff} B. M. at 303°K	Λ M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Absorption bands (cm ⁻¹)	Transition	Molar Extinction-Coeff (ϵ) mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
	Found	Calcd					
[CrL]	471	480	4.82	2.7	14300	⁶ E _g - ⁶ T _{2g}	44-50
[CrL']	(413)	(420)	(4.84)	(3.0)	(24800)		
[MnL]	475	483	5.91	3.2	24700	⁶ A _{1g} - ⁴ E _g (G)	54-71
[MnL']	(411)	(423)	(5.92)	(3.8)	(24800)		
					29900	⁶ A - ⁴ E _g (D)	68-86
					(30000)		
[FeL]	477	484	5.42	4.5	10200	⁶ T _{2g} - ⁶ E _g (D)	64-77
[FeL']	(413)	(424)	(5.44)	(4.4)	(10500)		
[CoL]	478	487	5.10	5.1	8400	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	69-76
[CoL']	(416)	(427)	(5.12)	(5.3)	(8700)		
					16200	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ A _{2g} (F)	89-91
					(16800)		
					20800	⁴ T _{1g} (F) - ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	96-102
					(21100)		
[NiL]	478	487	3.12	6.6	8700	⁶ A _{2g} (F) - ⁶ T _{2g} (F)	71-78
[NiL']	(417)	(427)	(3.14)	(6.8)	(9200)		
					13700	⁶ A _{2g} - ⁶ T _{1g} (F)	82-98
					(13900)		
					25600	⁶ A _{2g} - ⁶ T _{1g} (P)	99-110
					(26200)		
[CuL]	483	492	1.93	2.8	12800	⁶ E _g - ⁶ T _{2g}	122-132
[CuL']	(422)	(432)	(1.94)	(3.1)	(13300)		

where L=(C₁₁H₉NO₃)₂ and L'=(C₈H₁₀NO₄)₂

The values in parenthesis are those of the HFP chelates having the composition [(C₈H₁₀NO₄)₂M]. All the chelates gave satisfactory C, H, and N analysis.

In general the metal chelates display 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The molecular weight data suggest the composition $[ML_2]$ for these compounds, where M = metal-ion and LH = HFB or HFP. Their magnetic moments indicate the presence of 4, 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electron, respectively in the Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates.

A perusal of the μ_{eff} value suggest these complexes to be high-spin ones.

The data shown in Table 1 suggest nearly octahedral structure for these chelates. However, Cu(II) chelates may possess square-planar or tetragonally distorted octahedral structure in terms of Jahn-Teller effect⁶.

I. R. spectra of HFB and HFP show bands in the ranges of 2570-2560 cm^{-1} , 1690-1680 cm^{-1} and 1610-1600 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{COOH} , ν_{C-O} and ν_{C-N} , respectively. In the spectra of the metal chelates the bands in the range 2570-2560 cm^{-1} disappeared suggesting co-ordination through the carboxylate group and appearance of bands in the region 1560-1620 cm^{-1} and 1300-1380 cm^{-1} indicate $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_s(COO^-)$, respectively. ν_{C-N} of the ligands in the range 1610-1600 cm^{-1} was shifted to lower frequency side. On chelation suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in co-ordination. The appearance of two new bands in the ranges of 620-610 cm^{-1} and 550-540 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates indicate the formation of M-O and M-N bonds respectively in them. As regards the heterogeneity of ν_{M-O} band, it appears that perhaps due to interference by ligand molecule it is not discernible⁷.

The very low conductance values of the chelates in dioxan and DMF at room temperature suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The results so far obtained conclusively show that the general similarities of the chelates of HFB and HFP are not due to the presence or absence of an open chain or a six membered ring but it is due to the presence of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in β -position to the carboxylic group.

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Isolation and Characterization of Methyl N,N¹ ethylenebis (salicylidene iminato) cobalt (III)- μ -cyano-methyl-bis (dimethyl glyoximato) cobalt (III) anion as Tetra-Phenyl arsonium and Tetra ethyl ammonium Salts

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CYANO-COMPLEXES of cobalt, in its various oxidation states, are well known¹. Bridged cyanide complexes have also been postulated as intermediates^{2,3} in some inner-sphere electron transfer reaction of cyano cobalt compounds, and several such bridged complexes have been isolated⁴⁻⁷. Very few organo cyano cobalt (III) complexes are known in the solid state, although some of them are known to be formed in solution⁸.

One of our recent interests is to study the synthetic methods, reactivities and structural elucidation of some organo-derivatives of transition metal Schiff base complexes and analogous complexes⁹. It has been recognized for some time that the ligands trans to a σ -bonded alkyl substituent undergo substitution of rate much higher than the same ligand in similar compounds lacking the M-C σ bond¹⁰⁻¹⁷. This note describes our observations on the reactions of methyl aquo-N,N¹ ethylenebis (salicylidene iminato) cobalt (III), $CH_3Co(Salen)H_2O(I)^9$, with tetra phenyl arsonium/or tetra ethylammonium salt (S) of methyl bis(dimethyl glyoximato) cyano cobaltate (III), $M^+[CH_3Co(dmg)CN]$ (when, $M^+=Ph_4As^+(II)^8$ or $Et_4N^+(III)^8$) and the isolation and characterisation of the title cyano bridged complex, $M^+[CH_3Co(salen)CNCo(dmg)H]_2[CH_3]^-$ (when $M^+=Ph_4As(IV)$ and $M^+=Et_4N(V)$).

Treatment of (I) with the chloroform solution of (II) at $\sim 60^\circ$ yielded a brown solution. This brown solution, on treating with dry ether, gave a brown crystalline cyano-bridged complexes (IV). Analogously, the cyano bridged complex (V) was obtained when (I) was treated with (III). The molecular weight of (IV) supports its formulation. Besides, very satisfactory elemental analysis of C, H and N were obtained for (IV) and (V). [Found for (IV) : C, 58.38; H, 5.72; N, 9.58; Co, 11.09; M. wt. 1028. Calcd. for (IV) : C, 58.13; H, 5.13; N, 9.31; Co, 11.19 / M. wt. 1052.7. Found for (V) : C, 52.00; H, 6.97; N, 14.13; Co, 14.79; Calcd. for (V) : C, 52.52; H, 6.75; N, 14.01; Co, 4.7/].

The bridging nature of cyanide ions in these two complexes (IV) and (V) has been demonstrated by the cyanide stretching frequencies observed (at 2150 cm^{-1} and 2148 cm^{-1} respectively) in these two complexes⁸. The formation of bridged complexes has an effect on the infrared absorption of the bridged ligand. The cyanide stretching vibrations increase by a fairly constant increment over that of the monomeric complexes,